

ENA eDNA Data Submission Practical

As we have discussed, there are three routes of submission:

- Interactive
- Programmatic
- Webin-CLI

In this exercise, you will have the opportunity to submit a dataset comprised of raw read data and an ASV/OTU table to the test version of the **ENA submissions** service.

Webin Submissions Portal (TEST): <https://wwwdev.ebi.ac.uk/ena/submit/webin/login>

You will need an ENA Webin account to use for this exercise. Webin accounts can be registered on the webin portal 'Register' page:

<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/submit/webin/accountInfo>

The screenshot shows the 'Webin Submissions Portal' registration page. At the top, there is a header with the ENA logo and the text 'EUROPEAN GENOME-PHENOME ARCHIVE Webin Submissions Portal'. Below the header, the page is titled 'Account Management'. The main content area is divided into two columns. The left column is titled 'Account Details' and contains five input fields: 'Abbreviated center name', 'Full center name', 'Laboratory Name', 'Address', and 'Country'. The right column contains two input fields: 'Password' and 'Confirm Password'. Below the input fields, there is a section titled 'Contact Information' with a sub-header 'Add At Least One Contact' and a plus sign icon. At the bottom of the form, there is a section titled 'No Sensitive Data' with a checkbox and the text 'I confirm that the data submitted through this account is NOT sensitive, restricted-access or human-identifiable.'

For this practical, you will need the following file formats to complete your submission.

Each section of this practical will show what these files should look like:

1. study.json
2. run_experiment.xml
3. file_1_R1.fastq.gz

4. file_1_R2.fastq.gz
5. file_2_R1.fastq.gz
6. file_2_R2.fastq.gz
7. file_3_R1.fastq.gz
8. file_3_R2.fastq.gz
9. Analysis.xml
10. Soil_ASVsequences.fasta.gz
11. Soil_ASVtable.tsv.gz

It will be helpful to review how the metadata model works. You can find an overview of this here:

[Metadata Model](#)

Throughout this exercise, you are asked to use the ENA test service, which allows you to make submissions which will be removed after 24 hours. If you're not sure if you're in the test server, you can check the address in your browser which will begin 'wwwdev' rather than 'www':

<https://wwwdev.ebi.ac.uk/ena/submit/webin/login>

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The Scenario

Interested to learn about the plant diversity in forests in your study area, you have collected soil samples and used DNA metabarcoding methods. You have amplified a region of ITS2 and prepared a library for paired end sequencing on an Illumina MiSeq. After the demultiplexing you obtained a set of paired FASTQ files per analysed sample. You then proceeded to use your bioinformatic pipelines to filter and cluster the sequences according to the desired parameters and obtained a set of ASV sequences and the ASV table. Now it is time to submit your valuable data to the ENA!

You will start by registering a project/study programmatically, followed by registering three soil samples interactively. Then you will submit three paired fastq files (forward and reverse) and finally submit your ASV sequences and table programmatically to the ENA test submission service. The test submission service is identical to the production submission service, but submissions are retained for <24 hours. It's therefore perfect for training settings like this.

Some of these exercises require use of the command-line. Where there is a command to run, it will be provided for you mostly complete, indicated by an indented line beginning with a dollar ('\$') sign. Do not enter the \$, just the text following it. Some commands have been left incomplete for you to fill in, so read them carefully before you enter them.

The Study

To begin, you should **register a study**. Recall that a study describes the purpose of the work you have done, groups other objects beneath it, and controls when the data becomes public. A study is required for all submissions to ENA.

1. Please prepare a 'study.json' file in the following format:

```

{
  "submission": {
    "alias": "",
    "accession": "",
    "actions": [
      {
        "type": "ADD"
      },
      {
        "type": "HOLD",
        "holdUntilDate": "TO DO"
      }
    ]
  },
  "projects": [
    {
      "alias": "TO DO",
      "name": "TO DO",
      "title": "TO DO",
      "description": "TO DO",
      "sequencingProject": {},
      "attributes": [
        {
          "tag": "study keyword",
          "value": "metabarcoding"
        }
      ],
      "project_links": [
        {
          "xrefLink": {
            "db": "PUBMED",
            "id": "37143888"
          }
        }
      ]
    }
  ]
}

```

2. Try and understand the format of the JSON file and look for missing metadata that you will need to populate. This will be labelled as "TO DO".
3. The SUBMISSION file is merged with the project JSON. What "action" does the submission file indicate?

4. Set a **release date** for your study using HOLD in the submission section of the JSON file (this is when all data associated with the study will be released). This needs to be between now and a maximum of 2 years in the future.
5. The '**name**' field in the study json should be filled in with something brief and meaningful that can help you find and recognise the study.
6. You should take time to provide a descriptive title and informative abstract for your own studies, but these can be edited later if needed. The title could be something similar to:

Monitoring plant diversity through soil eDNA metabarcoding in <Your Region/Habitat>

7. Are there any publications to link to this study? If so please add them.
8. You now have the three essential components of a programmatic submission:
 - An account name and password
 - An object and its instruction to submit in JSON format
 - An endpoint to send this data to
9. Open a terminal window (CTRL+ALT+T or search) and navigate to the directory containing the files:

```
$ cd file/path
```

10. Type the 'ls' command to view the content of this directory:

```
$ ls -l
```

11. Enter the submission command below, editing it as you go to include the USERNAME, PASSWORD and submission file name.

```
curl -u username:password -X POST  
'https://wwwdev.ebi.ac.uk/ena/dev/submit/webin-v2/submit' -H  
'Accept: application/json' -H 'Content-Type: application/json'  
-T 'submission file name'
```

Note: If you are using windows terminal you may need to replace the single quotes by double quote

12. Upon successful submission, the terminal will return a success receipt with the project accession.

Make a note of its accession numbers, which will resemble:

ERP##### and PRJEB#####

Note: For a real submission, these would be the numbers you would cite in any publications involving the data.

The Sample

The next step is to register the samples, which will give other users essential context for the sequence data you are submitting. The samples describe the source biological material of your sequencing work. You will be registering **3 soil metagenome samples**.

In ENA, samples are required to conform to a checklist of values. Checklists define a set of mandatory and recommended values for a given type of sample. It is recommended that you look at these early and make sure you collect all required metadata items for the type of sample you will be registering.

The selection of available checklists can be browsed at:

<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/checklists>

1. Return to the main page of the Webin Portal and find the 'Samples' tab.

<https://wwwdev.ebi.ac.uk/ena/submit/webin/>

2. Click on the '**Register samples**' button.
3. Expand the section '**Download spreadsheet to register samples**'. You must choose an appropriate checklist of values to be provided for your sample. Browse the range of checklists available.

Note: Please make sure you use a MlxS checklist (Environmental checklist) for metagenomic data.

4. Which samples checklist do you feel is most relevant for the sample you have sequenced?
5. Submitters now have the option of including additional fields in their checklist. It is not necessary to include any additional fields but you can take this opportunity to see which fields are included as mandatory, recommended and optional, what requirements they have, and what else is available.

Click '**Next**' when you're ready.

6. Download the TSV template and open the file in Excel on your computer.

Please note that you should submit your spreadsheet in the same format that you have downloaded it (TSV).

7. When you open the TSV template, the 3rd row will state "#units". Please keep this row intact and enter your data from the 4th row as shown below. This is important for the system to successfully parse your tsv file:

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J
1	Checklist									
2	tax_id	scientific_name	sample_alias	sample_title	sample_description	project name	collection date	geographic location (latitude)	geographic location (longitude)	broad-scale environmental context
3	#units							DD	DD	
4										
5										

8. Find the appropriate taxon for your samples: to reiterate what we discussed during the presentation, please use a taxonomy that is as specific as possible. In this case for example, “**soil metagenome**” instead of just “**metagenome**”.

- a. This can be looked up on our rest API. Here is an example of a search for “metagenome”. You can search for the relevant taxonomy by replacing “metagenome” in the url below:

<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/taxonomy/rest/scientific-name/metagenome>

You can also search for the species name to find its tax ID on the NCBI Taxonomy database.

- b. NCBI Taxonomy database:

<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/taxonomy>

9. Give a 'Unique name' to your samples (sample_alias)

This value must always be unique among all samples submitted by your account and is a way for you to locate and recognise your specific samples.

10. Give your samples a title, this could look something like:

Soil metagenome sample x from <Your Region/Habitat>.

11. Write a brief description for your samples

12. Fill out the remaining details.

Tip: You can always find out more about what a field means and what information it accepts by going back to the checklist fields page on the Webin Portal and reading their description and validation.

Collection date format (year-month-date): 2024-10-24 , 2024-10 , 2024

13. By the time you have completed this, your samples will be well-annotated and understandable to people finding it in the database later. Click on ‘**Upload filled spreadsheet to register samples**’ on the Register Samples page and upload/submit the spreadsheet.

14. Now back on the main page, navigate to the 'Samples' tab to see the sample you just registered. You might need to refresh the page.

Make a note of its accession numbers as you will need these later:

ERS#####

The Read Data

Now that study and samples metadata have been registered, it is time to upload and submit the read data you have produced.

In this scenario, you will be submitting three paired set of files:

- file_1_R1.fastq.gz
- file_1_R2.fastq.gz
- file_2_R1.fastq.gz
- file_2_R2.fastq.gz
- file_3_R1.fastq.gz
- file_3_R2.fastq.gz

These are the raw read data files you have obtained as a result of sequencing your samples.

Upload Data Files

Before submitting the read data files, you must upload them. All Webin submission accounts come with a space on our server to upload files to. In most cases, submitters must upload their files to this before they are able to submit.

You will upload files to your private Webin file upload area using either FTP or Aspera protocol through the webin2.ebi.ac.uk service. The authentication is done using your Webin submission account name and password.

1. There are a number of tools and ways to accomplish the upload. For the purpose of this workshop, we will be using FileZilla to upload your read data files. Please install FileZilla client from here: <https://filezilla-project.org/>
2. Open the tool and enter the following details at the top before clicking "Quickconnect":

Host: webin2.ebi.ac.uk
Username: Webin-xxxx
Password: xxxx
3. Once it successfully establishes a connection, you have your local computer paths and files in the windows on the left, and the remote webin upload site on the right. Find the directory with the downloaded paired fastq files and drag the files into the directory listing at the remote site. This will upload your files to your webin upload area.

Submit Data Files

1. You will now be submitting your read files in XML file format. Start by preparing the run and experiment XML in the format shown below:

'run_experiment.xml'

```

<WEBIN>
  <SUBMISSION_SET>
    <SUBMISSION>
      <ACTIONS>
        <ACTION>
          <ADD/>
        </ACTION>
      </ACTIONS>
    </SUBMISSION>
  </SUBMISSION_SET>
  <EXPERIMENT_SET>
    <EXPERIMENT alias="soil_ITS_experiment_1">
      <TITLE>TO DO</TITLE>
      <STUDY_REF accession="PRJEB49250"/>
      <DESIGN>
        <DESIGN_DESCRIPTION/>
        <SAMPLE_DESCRIPTOR accession="SAMEA11243259"/>
        <LIBRARY_DESCRIPTOR>
          <LIBRARY_NAME/>
          <LIBRARY_STRATEGY>AMPLICON</LIBRARY_STRATEGY>
          <LIBRARY_SOURCE>METAGENOMIC</LIBRARY_SOURCE>
          <...>
          <...>
        </LIBRARY_DESCRIPTOR>
        <EXPERIMENT_ATTRIBUTES>
          <EXPERIMENT_ATTRIBUTE>
            <TAG>library preparation date</TAG>
            <VALUE>TO DO</VALUE>
          </EXPERIMENT_ATTRIBUTE>
        </EXPERIMENT_ATTRIBUTES>
      </EXPERIMENT>
    </EXPERIMENT_SET>
    <RUN_SET>
      <RUN alias="soil_run_1" center_name="">
        <EXPERIMENT_REF refname="soil_ITS_experiment_1"/>
        <DATA_BLOCK>
          <FILES>
            <FILE filename="file_1_R1.fastq.gz" filetype="fastq"
              checksum_method="MD5" checksum="23316bb71b291a61484d6b14d8ae453a"/>
            <FILE filename="file_1_R2.fastq.gz" filetype="fastq"
              checksum_method="MD5" checksum="40d636c363e1a3a5232d3d1e2feb2c70"/>
          </FILES>
        </DATA_BLOCK>
      </RUN>
    </RUN SET>
  
```

- Look at the different attributes contained within. Go through the experiments XML and add any missing metadata fields where you can see "TO DO" in the <VALUE></VALUE> tags.

Samples : enter an accession for the samples you registered earlier (ERS, ERS,..)

Study : enter an accession for the study you registered earlier (PRJEBxxx)

Library Name (Title): TO DO - your lab initials_sequence_library_1

Library Strategy : AMPLICON [Check permitted values](#)

Library Source : METAGENOMIC [Check permitted values](#)

Library Selection : PCR [Check permitted values](#)

Library Layout : PAIRED

Library Construction Protocol: TO DO - short description of the protocol

Instrument Model : Illumina MiSeq [Check permitted values](#)

Library Preparation Date: TO DO - Enter the date in the format
YYYY-MM-DD

- Go through the run XML to make sure all the fields have been populated and the type of information that is required for a run submission.

Forward File Name : file_1_R1.fastq.gz
File Md5 : [Calculate md5 checksum value](#)
Reverse File Name : file_1_R2.fastq.gz
File Md5 : [Calculate md5 checksum value](#)

Forward File Name : file_2_R1.fastq.gz
File Md5 : [Calculate md5 checksum value](#)
Reverse File Name : file_2_R2.fastq.gz
File Md5 : [Calculate md5 checksum value](#)

Forward File Name : file_3_R1.fastq.gz
File Md5 : [Calculate md5 checksum value](#)
Reverse File Name : file_3_R2.fastq.gz
File Md5 : [Calculate md5 checksum value](#)

- Next, look at the submission XML included within this file.
What action is specified for this submission?
- Save the XML file when you have completed the fields.

- You now have the three essential components of a programmatic submission:
 - An account name and password
 - An object and its instruction to submit in XML format
 - An endpoint to send this data to
- Open a terminal window (CTRL+ALT+T or search) and navigate to the directory containing the files:

```
$ cd file/path
```

- Type the 'ls' command to view the content of this directory:

```
$ ls -l
```

- Enter the submission command below, editing it as you go to include the USERNAME, PASSWORD and submission file name.

```
curl -u username:password -X POST  

'https://wwwdev.ebi.ac.uk/ena/dev/submit/webin-v2/submit' -H  

'Accept: application/xml' -H 'Content-Type: application/xml'  

-T 'submission file name'
```

Note: If you are using windows terminal you may need to replace the single quotes by double quote

5. Once a submission has been processed a receipt is returned. The **success** attribute in the receipt is **true** if the submission was successful and **false** if the submission was not successful. The receipt also contains the accession numbers of the objects that you have submitted. In this case you will receive three run accession (ERRxxx) and three experiment accession (ERXxxx)

The Environmental Sequence Set

The final step is to submit your OTU/ASV sequences and table. You will submit this programmatically.

You will be submitting a fasta file with the sequences and a tsv file (OTU/ASV table):

- Soil_ASVsequences.fasta.gz
- Soil_ASVtable.tsv.gz

Upload Data Files

Before submitting the analysis files, you must upload them.

You will again upload the files to your private Webin file upload area using FileZilla. The authentication is done using your Webin submission account name and password.

1. Open the tool and enter the following details at the top before clicking "Quickconnect":

Host: webin2.ebi.ac.uk
Username: Webin-xxxx
Password: xxxx

2. Once it successfully establishes a connection, you have your local computer paths and files in the windows on the left, and the remote webin upload site on the right. Find the directory with the downloaded fasta and tsv files and drag the files into the directory listing at the remote site. This will upload your files to your webin upload area.

Submit Data files

1. You will now be submitting your analysis files in XML file format. Your uploaded files should be in a similar format to that shown below:

'Soil_ASVsequences.fasta.gz'

```

>PRJEB12345_ASV1
ACTATGCTTAGCCCTAAACTTAAATAATTTAATAACAAAATATTTGCCAGAGAGCTACTAGCTACTGCTTAAACTCAAAGGACTTGGCGGTACTTTATATCCAT
>PRJEB12345_ASV2
GCTATGCTTAGCCATAAACCTAAATAATTTAAATTTAACAAAATATTTGCCAGAGAAGCTACTAGCCATAGCTTAAACTCAAAGGACTTGGCGGTACTTTATATCCG
>PRJEB12345_ASV3
ACTATGCTTAGCCCTAAACTTAAATAATTTAATAACAAAATATTTGCCAGAGAAGCTACTAGCTACTGCTTAAACTCGAAGGACTTGGCGGTACTTTATATCCAT
>PRJEB12345_ASV4
ACTATGCTTAGCCCTAAACCTCAACAGTTAAATCAACAAAATGCTCGCCAGAACACTACGAGCCACAGCTTAAACTCAAAGGACTTGGCGGTGCTTCATATCCCT
>PRJEB12345_ASV5
ACTATGCTTAGCCCTAAACTCAATAATTTAGAAAACAAAATATTTGCCTGAGAAGCTACTGGCCACAGCTTAAACTCAAAGGACTTGGCGGTACTTTATATCCAT
>PRJEB12345_ASV6
ACTATGCTTAGCCCTAAACTAAAACAATCAATAACAAAGACTGTTTCGCCAGAGAAGCTACTAGCAATAGCTTAAACTCAAAGGACTTGGCGGTGCTTTATATCCAT
>PRJEB12345_ASV7
ACTATGCTTAGCCCTAAACTTAAATAATTTAATAACAAAATATTTGCCAGAGAAGCTACTAGCTACTGCTTAAACTCAAAGGGCTTGGCGGTACTTTATATCCAT
>PRJEB12345_ASV8
ACTATGCTTAGCCCTAAACTTAAATGATTCTAAAACAAAATATTTGCCTGAGAAGCTACTGGCCACAGCTTAAACTCAAAGGACTTGGCGGTACTTTATATCCAT
>PRJEB12345_ASV9
ACTATGCTTAGCCCTAAACTTAAATAATTTAATAACAAAATATTTGCCAGAGAAGCTACTAGCTACTGCTTAAACTCAAAGGACTTGGCGGTACTTTATATCCAT
>PRJEB12345_ASV10
ACTATGCTTAGCCCTAAACTTAAATAATTTCTAAAACAAAATATTTGCCTGAGAATTAAGCTGGCCACAGCTTAAACTCAAAGGACTTGGCGGTACTTTATATCCAT
>PRJEB12345_ASV11
ACTATGCTTAGCCCTAAACTTAAATAATTTCTAAAACAAAATATTTGCCTGAGAAGCTACTGGCCACAGCTTAAACTCAAAGGACTTGGCGGTATTTTATATCCAT
>PRJEB12345_ASV12
ACTATGCTTAGCCCTAAACTGAAACAATCAATAACAAAGACTGTTTCGCCAGAGAAGCTACTAGCAATAGCTTAAACTCAAAGGACTTGGCGGTGCTTTATATCCAT
>PRJEB12345_ASV13
ACTATGCTTAGCCCTAAACTTAAATAATTTCTAAAACAAAATATTTGCCTGAGAAGCTACTGGCCACAGCTTAAACTCAAAGGACTTGGCGGTACTTTATATCCAT
>PRJEB12345_ASV14
ACTATGCTTAGCCCTAAACTAAAACAATCAATAACAAAGACTGTTTCGCCAGAGAAGCTACTAGCAATAGCTTAAACTCAAAGGACTTGGCGGTGCTTTATATCCAT
>PRJEB12345_ASV15
ACTATGCTTAGCCCTAAACTTAAATAATTTCTAAAACAAAATATTTGCCTGAGAAGCTACTGGCCACAGCTTAAACTCAAAGGACTTGGCGGTACTTTATATCCAT
>PRJEB12345_ASV16
ACTATGCTTAGCCCTAAACTAAAACAATCAATAACAAAGACTGTTTCGCCAGAGAAGCTACTAGCAATAGCTTAAACCCAAAGGACTTGGCGGTGCTTTATATCCAT
>PRJEB12345_ASV17
ACTATGCTTAGCCCTAAACTTAAATAATTTCTAAAACAAAATATTTGCCTGAGAAGCTACTGGCCACAGCTTAAACTCAAAGGACTTGGCGGTACTTTATATCCAT
>PRJEB12345_ASV18
ACTATGCTTAGCCCTAAACTAAAACAATCAATAACAAAGACTGTTTCGCCAGAGAAGCTACTAGCAGTAGCTTAAACTCAAAGGACTTGGCGGTGCTTTATATCCAT

```

'Soil_ASVtable.tsv.gz'

	A	B	C	D
1	Sequence_id	Sample_id	Frequency	
2	PRJEB12345_ASV1	SAMEA12345	30	
3	PRJEB12345_ASV10	SAMEA12346	9	
4	PRJEB12345_ASV10	SAMEA12347	13	
5	PRJEB12345_ASV11	SAMEA12348	23	
6	PRJEB12345_ASV12	SAMEA12349	3	
7	PRJEB12345_ASV12	SAMEA12350	5	
8	PRJEB12345_ASV12	SAMEA12351	25	
9	PRJEB12345_ASV13	SAMEA12352	16	
10	PRJEB12345_ASV14	SAMEA12353	8	
11	PRJEB12345_ASV14	SAMEA12354	10	
12	PRJEB12345_ASV15	SAMEA12355	9	
13	PRJEB12345_ASV15	SAMEA12356	2991	
14	PRJEB12345_ASV15	SAMEA12357	3289	
15	PRJEB12345_ASV16	SAMEA12358	11	
16	PRJEB12345_ASV17	SAMEA12359	5	
17	PRJEB12345_ASV17	SAMEA12360	12	
18	PRJEB12345_ASV18	SAMEA12361	23	

- Take a look at the contents of the fasta file using the 'zcat' command:

```
$ zcat Soil_ASVsequences.fasta.gz
```

Note: If you are using windows, you will need to gunzip the file and open it with notepad++

This is a simple fasta file containing the ASV sequences that derived from your analysis. Please note that sequence names should be unique.

3. Then, take a look at the tsv file

```
$ zcat Soil_ASVtable.tsv.gz
```

This is a three column table that represents the OTU/ASV matrix. The table contains three columns: `sequence_id` (that must match the names of the sequences in the fasta file), `sample_id` (the sample accession numbers used in your study) and `frequency` (the number of reads of each sequence in each sample).

4. Now you need to prepare the analysis XML for submission. Your file should be in a similar format to that shown below:

'analysis.xml'

```

</SUBMISSION_SET>
<ANALYSIS_SET>
  <ANALYSIS alias="TO DO">
    <TITLE>TO DO</TITLE>
    <DESCRIPTION>TO DO</DESCRIPTION>
    <STUDY_REF accession="TO DO"/>
    <RUN_REF accession="TO DO"/>
    <RUN_REF accession="TO DO"/>
    <RUN_REF accession="TO DO"/>
    <ANALYSIS_TYPE>
      <ENVIRONMENTAL_SEQUENCE_SET/>
    </ANALYSIS_TYPE>
    <FILES>
      <FILE filename="Soil_ASVsequences.fasta.gz" filetype="fasta"
        checksum_method="MD5" checksum="TO DO"/>
      <FILE filename="Soil_ASVtable.tsv.gz" filetype="tab"
        checksum_method="MD5" checksum="TO DO"/>
    </FILES>
    <ANALYSIS_ATTRIBUTES>
      <ANALYSIS_ATTRIBUTE>
        <TAG>target locus</TAG>
        <VALUE>TO DO</VALUE>
      </ANALYSIS_ATTRIBUTE>
      <ANALYSIS_ATTRIBUTE>
        <TAG>analysis protocol</TAG>
        <VALUE>TO DO</VALUE>
      </ANALYSIS_ATTRIBUTE>
      <ANALYSIS_ATTRIBUTE>
        <TAG>Analysis date</TAG>
        <VALUE>TO DO</VALUE>
        <UNITS>YYYY-MM-DD</UNITS>
      </ANALYSIS_ATTRIBUTE>
      <ANALYSIS_ATTRIBUTE>
        <TAG>Analysis code</TAG>
        <VALUE>TO DO</VALUE>
      </ANALYSIS_ATTRIBUTE>
      <ANALYSIS_ATTRIBUTE>
        <TAG>Analysis version</TAG>
        <VALUE>TO DO</VALUE>
      </ANALYSIS_ATTRIBUTE>
    </ANALYSIS_ATTRIBUTES>
  </ANALYSIS>
</ANALYSIS_SET>
</WEBIN>

```

- Look at the different attributes contained within. This contains some mandatory and optional metadata. It is possible to provide further metadata and this will be documented once implementation is complete. Go through the analysis XML and add any missing metadata fields where you can see “TO DO” in the <VALUE></VALUE> tags.

Title : “TO DO” - short title for your analysis e.g. “ITS2 ASV table from soil samples”

Description : “TO DO” -a short description of your analysis e.g. “ITS2 ASV table describing plant diversity from soil metabarcoding”

Study : enter an accession for the study you registered earlier (PRJEBxxx)

Run_ref : enter an accession for the runs you registered earlier (ERRx, ERRx, ERRx)

Analysis type : ENVIRONMENTAL SEQUENCE SET

Fasta File Name : Soil_ASVsequences.fasta.gz

File Md5 : 9ca5eb20eba13c239f5fbc3556c9dbd6

TSV File Name : Soil_ASVtable.tsv.gz

File Md5 : f8b36f2e38d42a6f0b2b5a3b43da61de

Target locus : "TO D0" - Targeted gene or locus name amplified

Analysis protocol : "TO D0" - Link to the description of the analysis protocol or an overview of the full analysis including names, references and versions of any software employed

Analysis date : "TO D0" - The date when this analysis was produced YYYY-MM-DD

Analysis code : "TO D0" - Link to the repository that contains the code used in the analysis

Analysis version : "TO D0" - Version of the analysis code used

6. Save the XML file when you have completed the fields.
6. You now have the three essential components of a programmatic submission:
 - An account name and password
 - An object and its instruction to submit in XML format
 - An endpoint to send this data to
7. Open a terminal window (CTRL+ALT+T or search) and navigate to the directory containing the files:

```
$ cd file/path
```

8. Type the 'ls' command to view the content of this directory:

```
$ ls -l
```

9. Enter the submission command below, editing it as you go to include the USERNAME, PASSWORD and submission file name.

```
curl -u username:password -X POST
'https://wwwdev.ebi.ac.uk/ena/dev/submit/webin-v2/submit' -H
'Accept: application/xml' -H 'Content-Type: application/xml'
-T 'submission file name'
```

Note: If you are using windows terminal you may need to replace the single quotes by double quote

10. Once a submission has been processed a receipt is returned. The **success** attribute in the receipt is **true** if the submission was successful and **false** if the submission was not successful. The receipt also contains the accession numbers of the objects

that you have submitted. In this case you will receive an analysis accession (ERZxxx).